

README

Folders Structure and Codes Description

Fig 2 & Fig 3 folder:

This folder contains two main scripts: “Analysis_Temp” and “Merge Temp”.

- Analysis_Temp: This script produces a continuous ensemble of Sea Surface Temperature (SST) measurements for the Ashdod and Haifa locations. It uses data from buoys along with supplementary datasets recorded at Palmahim (near Ashdod) and Shikmona (near Haifa).
- Merge_temp: This script fills gaps in the SST ensemble by choosing the dataset with the smallest deviation from the weekly mean value two weeks before the gap (Ashdod/Haifa, Palmahim, Shikmona). For gaps under 24 hours, linear interpolation is used.

Data files list:

- Haifa_Date_1_min_date_new.mat: 1-minute Datetime vector corresponding to 1 minute averaged SST data measured in Haifa.
- Haifa_data_1_min_new.mat: 1-minute averaged SST data measured in Haifa.
- Ashdod_Date_1_min_date_new.mat: 1-minute Datetime vector corresponding to 1 minute averaged SST data measured in Ashdod.
- Ashdod_data_1_min_new.mat: 1-minute averaged SST data measured in Ashdod.
- Palmahim_data_1_min_date.mat: 1-minute Datetime vector corresponding to 1 minute averaged SST data measured in Palmahim.
- Palmahim_data_1_min.mat: 1-minute averaged SST data measured in Palmahim.
- Haifa_SHIKMONA_data_1_min_date.mat: 1-minute Datetime vector corresponding to 1 minute averaged SST data measured in Shikmona.
- Haifa_SHIKMONA_data_1_min.mat: 1-minute averaged SST data measured in Shikmona.

Figures:

- Fig2_SST_WITH_GAPS
 - Fig3_Continoues_SST
-

Fig 4, 5, 6 & 7 folder:

This folder contains the script: “climate_change”.

- climate_change: This script analyzes the SST trends (annually, seasonally, and monthly) and seasonal shifts while comparing measured SST data with OISST NOAA V2 and ERA5 reanalyzed models products.

Data files list:

- T_S_A_new.mat: Continuous SST data for Ashdod.
- T_S_DA_new1.mat: Datetime vector corresponding to continuous SST data for Ashdod.
- T_S_H_new1.mat: Continuous SST data for Haifa.
- T_S_DH_new1.mat: Datetime vector corresponding to continuous SST data for Haifa.

Auxiliary folders list:

- Copernicus: ERA5 model data used in this research (.mat files).
- NOAA: No files are included. The NOAA OI-SST V2 data is freely available at the NOAA website <https://psl.noaa.gov/data/gridded/data.noaa.oisst.v2.highres.html> .

Figures:

- Fig4_Annual_and_Seasonal_SST_Average_trends_Ashdod
- Fig4_Annual_and_Seasonal_SST_Average_trends_Haifa
- Fig 5 30 years trend each month Ashdod_new
- Fig 5 30 years trend each month Haifa_new
- Fig 6 Ashdod_and_Haifa_4D
- Fig 7 below left Autumn _ change
- Fig 7 low right spring
- Fig 7 up left Ashdod_season_durations
- Fig 7 up right Haifa_season_durations

Fig 8 & 9 folder:

This folder contains two main scripts: "HEATWAVES_ANALYSIS" and "HEATWAVES_INDEX".

- HEATWAVES_ANALYSIS: This script identifies and presents Marine Heatwaves accompanied by relevant statistics.
- HEATWAVES_INDEX: This script calculates climatology and the 90th percentile from the continuous SST data for Haifa and Ashdod. It compares these values with raw SST data (after normalization). The analysis follows the methods described in Hobday (2016, 2018).

Data files list:

- T_S_A_new.mat: Continuous SST data for Ashdod.
- T_S_DA_new1.mat: Datetime vector corresponding to continuous SST data for Ashdod.
- T_S_H_new1.mat: Continuous SST data for Haifa.
- T_S_DH_new1.mat: Datetime vector corresponding to continuous SST data for Haifa.
- Haifa_T_new1.mat: Raw SST data measured near Haifa.

- Ashdod_T_new1.mat: Raw SST data measured near Ashdod.
- dateA_new1.mat: Corresponding dates to raw SST data measured near Ashdod.
- dateH_new1.mat: Corresponding dates to raw SST data measured near Haifa.
- Heatwaves Haifa.xlsx: Heatwaves statistics and dates occurred in Haifa.
- Heatwaves Ashdod.xlsx: Heatwaves statistics and dates occurred in Ashdod.

Figures:

- Fig8_HeatWaves
 - Fig9_Heatwaves Statistics
-

Fig 10 & Fig 11 folder:

This folder contains two main scripts: "History_of_Hs" and "long_term_statistics"

- History_of_Hs: This script presents the significant wave height (Hs) values over 30 years from both, Haifa and Ashdod, locations. It also calculates the trend for rogue waves occurrences ($H > 2H_s$).
- long_term_statistics: This script calculates annual extremes and compares them to four different long-term distributions: lognormal, extreme values, generalized extreme values, and Weibull.

Data files list:

- No files are included. The XLSX files for Ashdod and Haifa buoys data, required to run the scripts, are owned by the CAMERI LTD and can be obtained through direct purchase from CAMERI LTD, Israel. <https://www.cameri-eng.com/>

Figures:

- Fig_10_Hs_History
 - Fig_11_Long_terms_distributions
-

Fig 12 folder:

This folder contains one main script: "storm_above_3_dates"

- storm_above_3_dates: This script is used to identify a trend in storm occurrences while using fft and low pass filter, filtering out short-term variations.

Figures:

- Fig 12 Storm Occurrences and fft_NEW
-

Fig 13, 14 & 15 folder:

This folder contains one main script: "wave_events_composite"

- wave_events_composite: The script produces atmospheric anomalies plots. Lines 41 to 84 convert the list of dates to a datenum. Lines 93 to 185 load in ERA5 data. Lines 191 to 501 make the actual figures.

Data files list:

- No files are included. The ERA5 data is freely available at the Copernicus website. <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/reanalysis-era5-single-levels?tab=download> [last access: November 28, 2024]

Figures:

- Fig_13_maps_ashdod_only
- Fig_14_maps_haifa_only
- Fig_15_maps_both

Note: These figures are available in EPS format.

Fig 16 folder:

This folder contains one main script and three auxiliary scripts: "Rogue_waves_analysis" and "zero_crossing", "spectral", "spectr_moments2".

- Rogue_waves_analysis: This script calculates statistics for rogue waves recorded by the buoys, based on the standard rogue wave threshold ($H > 2H_s$).
- zero_crossing: This script calculates the statistics of crests, troughs, and wave heights for each dataset.
- spectral: This script produces the wave field spectrum, including energy density spectrum (S), Fourier components (Y), and frequency vector (f).
- spectr_moments2: This script calculates spectral moments (m0 to m4) and the significant wave height (H_s).

Note: The History_of_Hs script was used before and created a bar plot that can be found in Fig. 16 folder.

Auxiliary folder:

- Rogue waves datasets (contain .txt files of water surface elevation derived from buoy data)

Figures:

- Fig_16_upper_panel_Rogue_Waves_bar_plot
- Fig_16_rw_crest_vs_Hs
- Fig_16_Rogue_Waves_H_over_Hs
- Fig_16_lower_panel_rw_11.5_m

Fig 17 folder:

This folder contains one main script: "sstdrop"

- sstdrop: This script calculates the trends of SST drop occurrences as measured by the both buoys.

Figures:

- Fig 17 right SST OCCUERNCES_new
 - Fig 17 left SST DROPS AND RAPID RISE OF SST_new
-

Fig 18 folder:

This folder contains one main script: "SST_DROP_ANALYSIS2"

- SST_DROP_ANALYSIS2: This script analyzes the statistical dependency between SST drops and storm intensity (Hs), storm mixing through spectral peak wave periods, and the duration of mixing from SST drop to storm peak. The analysis is applied to both Ashdod (A) and Haifa (H) locations data.

Data files list:

- TpA.mat: Waves time periods at the spectral peak, for the peak of storm event measured in Ashdod.
- Tph.mat: Waves time periods at the spectral peak, for the peak of storm event measured in Haifa.
- Temp_Haifa_sst_drop.xlsx: List of SST drop events dates, temperatures and significant wave height measured near Haifa.
- Temp_Ashdod_sst_drop.xlsx: List of SST drop events dates, temperatures and significant wave height measured near Ashdod.

Figures:

- Fig18_SSTD_STATISTICS
-

Fig 19 folder:

This folder contains three main scripts: "sl_acre", "SL_Ashkelon" and "SL_TLV_Jaffo".

- These scripts calculate the mean annual (and monthly) sea level rise for three locations: Acre, Ashkelon, and Tel Aviv-Jaffo.

Data files list:

- sea level -TLV 1996-2010 - Jaffo 2011 - 2022 spt.txt
- Sea Level - Ashkelon 2000 - 2022 spt.txt
- acre 2005 - 2022 aug.txt

Figures:

- Fig19 NEW sl
-

Fig 20 & 21 folder:

This folder contains one main script: "CORRELATION".

- CORRELATION: This script calculates the Pearson correlation coefficients between Sea Surface Temperatures (SST) and Sea Level Rise ensembles.

Data files list:

- ssl_t.mat: Sea Surface Level annual average measured in TLV Jaffe marina.
- sst_A_H.mat: SST annual average measured in Ashdod and Haifa.

Figures:

- Fig_20_MWL
 - Fig_21_CORRELATION
-

Additional data files:

The raw SST data from Palmahim and Shikmona are found in the main folder under

- 9.3.09-18.9.22 Palmahim initial analysis.xls – raw temperature records.
- SHIKMONA 9.3.10 - 1.12.22.xls - raw temperature records.

General Notes:

- Please ensure the correct path is specified in all instances where "path..." is mentioned.
- Clean, 1-minute versions of these files are available in the Fig 2 & Fig 3 folder.
- For any further questions, feel free to contact Sagi Knobler (sagikn@campus.technion.ac.il) or Dan Liberzon (liberzon@technion.ac.il).